

The Lived Experiences of Covid-19 Survivors in Surigao City

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Abstract

The study explored the lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors in Surigao City. This qualitative study used Colaizzi's (1978) descriptive phenomenology. The researchers have had their informant sourcing completed using the purposive and snowball sampling methods to find the twelve (12) people needed for this study. The researchers have utilized a researcher-made semi-structured interview in data generation. Eight core emergent themes developed from the seventeen cluster themes that emerged during data analysis using Colaizzi's (1978) method to describe the lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors. The data analysis findings allowed for an in-depth description of the phenomenon's lived experience. Even though treatments and a cure for COVID-19 are already available, the trauma it left behind remains, necessitating appropriate mental health intervention. However, comprehending survivors' difficulties and psychological disturbances may aid mental health professionals in taking steps to mitigate their traumatic experiences. Consequently, the survivors may have varied experiences with COVID-19, yet they remain grateful, compassionate, and resilient despite their adversities.

Keywords: *COVID-19 Survivors, Lived Experiences, Psychological & Physiological Disturbances, Vigilance, Spirituality, Resiliency*

Introduction

Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has become a global issue due to its higher mortality rate and pandemic health crisis. According to Munawar and Choudhry (2021), healthcare systems and people must prepare medically and psychologically while the outbreak is still happening. However, a pandemic health crisis was inept in the Philippines, and no one prepared for the outbreak. A lot of medical frontliners died to save lives despite uncertainty. According to World Health Organization (WHO) global figures, the COVID-19 death rate was 7% (Moradi et al., 2020).

Surigao City is in Mindanao, particularly in the Caraga region, and according to the Surigao City Planning Office (2022), the city's total population is 171, 107 based on a 2020's survey. In addition, Surigao City is one of the places where the disease entered and continuously spread. Surigao City reported in 2020 that the disease had begun to spread and afflicted several people. Based on the statistical data given, out of 371 (0.22%) cases in the year 2020, 36 people died. Therefore, 335 have recovered from the disease. In 2021, the total confirmed cases increased by up to 5.8%; the total recovered cases were 2,323, and the number of deaths was about 169 out of the 2,513 (1.5%) confirmed cases. In 2022, from January to February, the number of deaths based on the cumulative data was 179 out of 2,711 (1.6%) cases, and 2,509 have recovered. The data shows that the cases have increased by 7.9% regardless of whether the patient had experienced symptomatic, was asymptomatic, or had gone through an intensive care unit (ICU) (City Health Office, 2022).

Due to the anxiety and spirituality underlying the pandemic, the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) impacts many facets of people's lives. However, mainly on mental health (Rathakrishnan et al., 2022), the situation prompted the researchers to conduct this study to explore the lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors and how they were affected psychosocially.

Philosophical Underpinnings

This study was a phenomenological approach. Phenomenology study explores lived experiences to learn more about how individuals interpret those experiences (Ho & Limpaecher, 2022). Following data collection and analysis using phenomenological psychological reduction, descriptive phenomenological techniques make an effort to characterize the experiences lived through (Meyer, 2019). Husserl's phenomenological approach, on the other hand, is the study of human beings at a deeper level through observing phenomena. It is a philosophy and a method of inquiry used to understand the lived reality of human beings at a conscious level (Morrow, 2018). Similarly, Colaizzi's (1978) descriptive phenomenology is a way of thoroughly understanding people's lived experiences rather than conceiving or developing theories as it reveals the experience of the phenomenon studied.

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Moreover, the researchers have also incorporated epistemology as a stance because the philosophy of knowing, epistemology, concerns how and from what sources information have gained. Regarding research, the researcher's philosophical viewpoint on the world and knowledge significantly impacts how he or she interprets evidence. Hence, his or her philosophical position should be stated clearly from the beginning (Brown, 2022). In modern epistemology, phenomenology aids in defining the phenomena based on knowledge assertions, whereas phenomenology claims to gain first-person knowledge of the nature of consciousness through intuition (Smith, 2013). Equally important, an epistemological perspective provides a basis for predicting, describing, enabling, and deconstructing population-specific worldviews, expanding the body of knowledge that leads to a better understanding of qualitative research's aim (Merriam, 2009, as cited by Hautly, 2020), as well as how you acquire and evaluate facts is heavily influenced by your understanding of knowledge and truth (Brown, 2022). Epistemology reflects researchers' worldviews and guides how they conduct research (Cal & Tehmarn, n.d.). This premise is consistent with Husserl's and Colaizzi's phenomenology: gaining a conscious understanding of an individual's lived experiences. For Colaizzi, using his method, people's experiences can be consistently understood as it helps uncover authentic meanings (Wirihana et al., 2018). Moreover, the researchers chose Colaizzi's phenomenology as it allows them to delve further into the lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors and explore their perspectives on the possible scenarios they have experienced.

Colaizzi's (1978) seven-stage process also ensures a thorough examination, with each phase remaining true to the facts. The outcome is a succinct yet comprehensive explanation of the phenomenon under investigation, validated by the people who generated it. The method relies upon comprehensive first-person accounts of experience gathered through face-to-face interviews, written narratives, blogs, research diaries, and internet interviews (Morrow et al., 2015). Furthermore, Colaizzi's phenomenological approach of seven steps refers to transcribing all the subject's description; extracting significant statements; creating formulated meanings; building themes; developing a detailed description; identifying the fundamental structure of the phenomenon; and returning to participants for validation.

Methods and Materials

This study used a qualitative approach employing Colaizzi's (1978) descriptive phenomenology to investigate and understand survivors' life experiences, challenges, and well-being because of the Coronavirus Disease 2019. This method would also uncover the authentic experience of the phenomenon under research (Colaizzi, 1978). Through the colaizzi's approach, the informants have shared their personal takes, perspectives, and situations, allowing the researchers to explore and assess these experiences extensively.

The researchers completed their informant sourcing using the purposive and snowball sampling methods to find the twelve (12) people needed for this study. The age range of all the informants in this study was 28 to 65. The researchers interviewed one (1) businessman, 65, and one (1) businesswoman, 55. One (1) government employee, one (1) MEPEO section manager, and

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eight (8) policemen and policewomen ranging in age from 28 to 35. Thus, the researchers interviewed five (5) men and seven (7) women in this study. Furthermore, purposive sampling is a technique in which the researchers select informants who must meet the criteria needed in the study. This approach was appropriate for phenomenological studies because the informants must have experienced a particular phenomenon. On the other hand, the snowball sampling approach has helped the researchers find the informants through referrals. Hence, the study chose the informants based on the following inclusion criteria:

1. Those that have been diagnosed with COVID-19;
2. Had been admitted at the hospital or admitted at COVID-19 facilities; and
3. Have fully recovered.

The researchers used a researcher-made semi-structured interview in data generation. The questions formulated aimed to understand the whole experience of the individuals within the current phenomenon. Probing questions served as manual questions to clarify and ensure the widespread points within the informants' responses. Furthermore, the interviews began with small talk to build a rapport with each informant.

Results and Discussion

The data gathered was analyzed using the Colaizzi's phenomenological approach: transcribing all the subject's description, extracting significant statements, creating formulated meanings, building themes, developing an exhaustive description, identifying the fundamental structure of the phenomenon, and returning to participants for validation. Results are shown in the following tables:

Table 1 shows *The Psychological and Physiological Disturbances: Survivors' psychological, emotional, and physical challenges have led to anxiety, fear, sadness, trauma, exhaustion, discomfort, and struggle. This theme was formulated out of the significant statements being extracted. The cluster themes formed are anxiety, fear, sadness, and trauma.*

Reference Number	Formulated Meanings	Cluster Themes	Themes
A10	Avoiding social gatherings to prevent oneself from getting re-infected by the disease.		
B14	Persistent to be admitted to isolate oneself and prevent the disease from spreading inside the house and infecting loved ones.		
C25	Anxious as to when one would recover.		

D30	Anxious of being alone and having no one to talk to about what one's going through.	Anxiety	<p>The Psychological and Physiological Disturbances:</p> <p>Survivors' psychological, emotional, and physical challenges have led to anxiety, fear, sadness, trauma, exhaustion, discomfort, and struggle</p>
D37	Having lots of thoughts because of the situation one was in.		
F42	COVID has negatively affected the extraverts, as they get anxious in their surroundings.		
F46	Initiated to distance oneself, thinking that people might feel disgusted.		
G54	Tend to get more anxious about her hygiene.		
I57	Having feelings of stress, hopelessness, and sadness when the swab test result was received.		
I58	Having anxiety because, as seen on television, many people died due to COVID.		
L71	Doesn't like to talk about COVID-19 because it was so traumatizing that his brother died because of it.		
L78	Disinfecting oneself with alcohol and wearing another set of clothes outside the house to avoid any trace of the virus.		
A12	Not attending the mass out of fear of getting infected again.		
A13	Afraid of losing one's life because of COVID.		
C24	Afraid of having physical contact with a stranger.		
D29	Keeping all of your pain to yourself and not telling your family about your situation.		
D31	Afraid that his family would feel frightened given the same experience he had with his brother.		
D36	Afraid that someone would make a hurtful or humiliating remark after the recovery.		
F44	Afraid that others would make a negative remark.		

F47	Feeling ashamed and one's self-esteem were affected due to how she perceived things, such as the rules that should be followed and what someone would think of her.	Fear	
I60	Their car wash business was affected because no one wanted to have their car cleaned, afraid that they may get infected with the disease.		
K67	Afraid to infect her children.		
L77	Avoiding social interaction, even with friends, to avoid re-infection.		
B18	Feeling sad that a COVID patient would be buried without the presence of relatives.	Sadness	
C27	They were desperate to see their families because they were lonely.		
J63	They were lonely because they were not allowed to go outside to prevent the virus from spreading.		
K66	Felt sad when she found out that she tested positive for COVID.		
L70	Had a traumatic experience with COVID-19 because his brother tested positive for the same diagnosis.	Trauma	
C20	Having the feeling of discomfort and exhaustion because of the COVID symptoms.	Exhaustion	
C22	Discomfort because of the sore throat.		

D28	Having COVID symptoms was stressful.	Discomfort	
D32	Doesn't want to make his family worry hence, handling the symptoms for ten days without letting his family know about it.	Struggle	
G51	Having a peculiar situation in which one cannot do the things she normally does.		
G52	One's outgoing personality suffers as a result of isolation.		
K65	Had unidentified feelings and missed her loved ones.		
K68	COVID-19 symptoms were difficult to handle.		
L73	Having mental, emotional, and spiritual difficulties.		

Table 2 shows *the Vigilance of being the Carrier: The fear of disease transmission which has led to cautiousness, social responsibility, guilt, and sympathy.*

A1	Protecting oneself against the disease through isolation.		
A6	Become more cautious.		
A9	Not staying in the crowd to maintain social distancing.		

B14	Insist on being admitted to isolation to prevent the disease from spreading inside the house and infecting loved ones.	Cautiousness	<p>Vigilance of being the Carrier:</p> <p>The fear of disease transmission which have led to cautiousness, social responsibility, guilt, and sympathy.</p>
B19	Become more cautious about one's health.		
B15	Showing concern and care for loved ones, thereby distancing oneself to prevent the virus from spreading.		
F43	Learning to adjust and distance oneself from others.		
G55	Disinfecting oneself and changing of clothes before entering the house.		
A3	Not afraid of losing income hence, closed the stores for the safety of everyone including their workers.	Social Responsibility	
A4	Responsible enough to submit oneself and ask for medical professional help.		
A5	Providing support to workers who were diagnosed with COVID-19.		
E40	Submitting oneself to professional help can prevent the virus from spreading.		
L72	Feeling guilty and blaming herself for his brother's death.	Guilt	
L74	Questioning God about his brother's death when it should have been her since she supposes that she was the carrier of the virus that infected her brother.		
B17	Showing care and sympathy with other patients who were unable to obtain their vital signs.	Sympathy	
D33	Having sympathy for another patient who was unable to be isolated in a better facility.		
G53	Showing more concern about others.		

Table 3 illustrates Spirituality: The outcome of one's isolation became a sense of connection where strengthening of faith results in a realization, trust, opportunity, and appreciation.

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A11	Realizing that life is too short and putting one's faith in God through praying.	Realization	Spirituality: The outcome of one's isolation became a sense of connection where strengthening of faith results in a realization, trust, opportunity, and
D38	Realizing that life is too short and prevention is better than cure.		
D39	Asking for God's help and enlightenment.		
F50	Realizing how beautiful life is and how it strengthens one's relationship with God.		
K69	Recognizing the importance of prayer and how it can help you by alleviating your dilemmas.	Faith	
L75	She was able to recover because of her faith in God.		
L76	Has a firm belief in God and believes that everything, including his brother's death, has a purpose.		
L80	Faith in God has become stronger.		
B16	Knowing how to obtain one's vital signs was beneficial.	Opportunity	
I59	COVID has helped her relax.		
I61	Considering how beneficial her isolation was, as it helped her relax and set things aside for the meantime.	Appreciation	
F48	Appreciating the lessons COVID has taught.		
F49	COVID provided time to reflect and appreciate life.		
H56	COVID-19 taught to appreciate life.		
L79	Appreciating how beautiful life is.		

Table 4. *Resiliency amidst COVID-19 Circumstance: The ability to adapt, accept and recover from the challenges, as well as the suffering and unpleasantness endured by the survivors, helps them gain resilience to face the trials.*

L81	Her experience made her become stronger.	Resilience	Resiliency amidst COVID-19 Circumstance:
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			The ability to adapt, accept and recover from the challenges
J64	The quarantine had an impact on his job and parental responsibilities.	Trial	

Figure 2. Emergent Model of the Lived Experiences of COVID-19 Survivors.

Conclusion

The lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors varied from one patient to another, resulting in four (4) emerging themes such as psychological and physiological disturbances, vigilance of being the carrier, spirituality, and resiliency amidst COVID-19 circumstance. Even if treatments and vaccines for COVID-19 are now available, the trauma it left behind is still present.

Moreover, the survivors have not heard nor received negative remarks about them being COVID patients isolated in a facility, but their families did. The survivors chose not to react and understand the people who discriminated against their family. Some of the survivors also mentioned that they did not feel any discrimination from people but received COVID jokes from their friends after recovering from the disease and returning to work. Even so, they still considered it as a friendly joke only. Furthermore, some survivors became grateful because they were asymptomatic, while those who were symptomatic, survived and their faith in God became stronger. Consequently, the survivors may have varied experiences with COVID-19, yet they remain grateful, compassionate, and resilient despite their adversities.

Implication

The following are the implications in light of the findings and conclusions:

COVID-19 Survivors. The findings of this study would make it possible for them to be heard and understood. May this study serve as how they can be helped and attain acceptance from society. The idea would make it easier for survivors to live without fear of discrimination or prejudice.

Citizens. The results of this research would enlighten the public regarding the experiences of COVID-19 survivors and what they have endured while coping with the disease. The findings would also help them realize that insensitive COVID remarks are never acceptable, regardless of the addressee. Therefore, sensitivity, understanding, and empathy are required to reduce such acts.

Practitioners in the Medical and Mental Health Fields. This study's findings serve as a primary source for determining the effects of COVID-19 on infected individuals. They would aid in the development of a mental health intervention plan.

Government. The findings of this study could provide them with the knowledge and information they may seek about mental health and help them understand the experiences of COVID-19 survivors and develop initiatives to prevent discrimination.

Psychology Students. The findings of this study would assist them in determining the effectiveness of mental health concerning the COVID-19 survivors' experiences and eradicating the stigma.

Future Researchers. This study's findings can serve as a foundation for future research. The results would also serve as a background or summary for topics related to COVID-19 and raise awareness of the struggles COVID-19 survivors confront.

References

- Brown, N. (2022, February 3). *Epistemology*. Dr Nicole Brown. <https://www.nicole-brown.co.uk/epistemology/>
- Caliwan, C. L. (2020, October 19). *Covid-19 survivors' tales: Isolated but not neglected*. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1118735>
- City health office .(2020). *Severity cases of COVID-19*. Surigao City.
- City health office .(2021). *Figures of Confirmed Cases of COVID-19*. Surigao City.
- City health office .(2022). *Figures of Confirmed Cases of COVID-19*. Surigao City.
- Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)*. (2022, December 19). Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/dotw/covid-19/index.html>
- Colaizzi, P. F. (1978). *Psychological research as the phenomenologist views it*. <https://philpapers.org/rec/COLPRA-5>
- Corpuz, J. C. G. (2021). Reflection: Spirituality during COVID-19. *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling: Advancing Theory and Professional Practice Through Scholarly and Reflective Publications*, 75(2), 133–134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1542305020985173>
- Hautly, L. (2020, December 11). *Epistemological Perspectives In Qualitative Research*. Lisa Hautly. [https://lisahautly.com/blog/epistemological-perspectives-in-qualitative-research#:~:text=An%20epistemological%20perspective%20provides%20a,research%20\(Merriam%2C%202009\).](https://lisahautly.com/blog/epistemological-perspectives-in-qualitative-research#:~:text=An%20epistemological%20perspective%20provides%20a,research%20(Merriam%2C%202009).)

- Jesmi, A. (2020). Lived experiences of patients with COVID-19 infection: A phenomenology study. *Lived Experiences of Patients with COVID-19 Infection: A Phenomenology Study*, 1–9. https://ljkzedo.ba/mgpdf/mg34/15_Jesmi_1247_A.pdf
- Meyer, A. (2019). *A Phenomenological Study of the Lived Experiences of Counseling Students in a Co-Facilitated Experiential Group*. ScholarWorks@UARK.
<https://scholarworks.uark.edu/etd/3272>
- Moradi, Y., Mollazadeh, F., Karimi, P., Hosseingholipour, K., & Baghaei, R. (2020). Psychological disturbances of survivors throughout COVID-19 crisis: a qualitative study. *BMC Psychiatry*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-03009-w>
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2015, August 1). *Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method*. CORE Reader. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/30734430>
- Munawar, K., & Choudhry, F. R. (2021). Exploring stress coping strategies of frontline emergency health workers dealing Covid-19 in Pakistan: A qualitative inquiry. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 49(3), 286–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2020.06.214>
- Qutoshi, S. B. (2018). Phenomenology: A Philosophy and Method of Inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), 215.
<https://doi.org/10.22555/joed.v5i1.2154>
- Rathakrishnan, B., Singh, S. S. B., Yahaya, A., Kamaluddin, M. R., & Aziz, S. F. A. (2022). The Relationship Among Spirituality, Fear, and Mental Health on COVID-19 Among Adults: An Exploratory Research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.815332>

- Romulo, S. G., & Urbano, R. C. (2022). Separation and Discrimination: The Lived Experience of COVID-19 Survivors in Philippine Isolation Centers. *Illness, Crisis & Loss*, 105413732210900. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10541373221090019>
- Shaban, R. Z., Nahidi, S., Sotomayor-Castillo, C., Li, C., Gilroy, N., O'Sullivan, M. V., Sorrell, T. C., White, E., Hackett, K., & Bag, S. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 infection and COVID-19: The lived experience and perceptions of patients in isolation and care in an Australian healthcare setting. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 48(12), 1445–1450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2020.08.032>
- Smith, D. (2013, December 16). *Phenomenology* (*Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*). Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/phenomenology/>
- Son, H. M., Choi, W. H., Hwang, Y. H., & Yang, H. R. (2021). The Lived Experiences of COVID-19 Patients in South Korea: A Qualitative Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(14), 7419. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18147419>
- Sreenivas, S. (2021, September 1). *What Is COVID-19 Fatigue?* WebMD. <https://www.webmd.com/lung/covid-fatigue>
- Sun, N., Wei, L., Wang, H., Wang, X., Gao, M., Hu, X., & Shi, S. (2021). Qualitative study of the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 278, 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.08.040>
- Tee, M. L., Tee, C. A., Anlacan, J. P., Aligam, K. J. G., Reyes, P. W. C., Kuruchittham, V., & Ho, R. C. (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 277, 379–391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.08.043>

Upenieks, L. (2022). Religious/spiritual struggles and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: Does “talking religion” help or hurt? *Review of Religious Research*, 64(2), 249–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13644-022-00487-0>

What Is a Pandemic? (2005, December 21). WebMD. <https://www.webmd.com/cold-and-flu/features/what-is-pandemic>

Wirihana, L., Welch, A., Williamson, M., Christensen, M., Bakon, S., & Craft, J. (2018). Using Colaizzi’s method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), 30–34. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e1516>